

A Digital Twin Framework for ^{153}Sm Medical Isotope Production in the UT-Austin TRIGA Reactor

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ABSTRACT

We present a digital twin (DT) for medical isotope irradiation campaigns on the University of Texas at Austin TRIGA Mark II research reactor. The DT couples six physics modules—temperature feedback, fission product poison kinetics, cross-section interpolation, two-group diffusion, control rod search, and target activation/depletion—with a reduced-order modeling and machine learning pipeline that predicts the full $\sim 7,000$ -DOF spatial neutron flux field in milliseconds. Using the VERA/MPACT transport solver, we generated hundreds of 2D training cases spanning the reactor operational parameter space and compressed them via SVD/POD into 6 basis modes. A LightGBM surrogate maps the operating-conditions state vector ζ_{ops} directly to POD coefficients, enabling real-time flux reconstruction and ^{153}Sm end-of-irradiation activity prediction. To our knowledge, this is the first planning-grade digital twin for medical isotope production in a research reactor.

Keywords: Digital Twin, Medical Isotopes, SVD/POD, Reduced Order Model (ROM), Machine Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

Over 691 million radiologic, computed tomography scans, dental, and nuclear medicine studies were performed in the United States in 2016, which represented 16.5% of the 4.2 billion performed worldwide [1]. This trend is continuing to increase rapidly with more procedures today than ever before. Yet the supply of critical medical isotopes—including ^{99m}Tc , ^{153}Sm , and ^{177}Lu —remains fragile. Production depends on a small number of aging international reactors, and radiopharmaceuticals cannot be stockpiled because they decay on timescales of hours to days. In late 2024 the unplanned shutdown of the High Flux Reactor in Petten, Netherlands, during a concurrent producer outage threatened a 50% reduction in ^{99m}Tc supply over three weeks, causing tens of thousands of canceled or delayed procedures for patients [2]. A 2025 DOE–NIH workshop report explicitly called for AI/ML and digital twin technologies to (i) optimize radionuclide yield, (ii) enable patient-specific dosimetry, and (iii) shorten the path to clinical adoption [3]. To our knowledge, no such tools currently exist for the TRIGA reactor.

The MIP-DT is built to model the University of Texas at Austin’s 1.1 MW TRIGA Mark II reactor and targets ^{153}Sm production via this reaction in Equation 1. ^{153}Sm is a beta emitter ($t_{1/2} = 46.3$ h) used for palliative treatment of bone metastases, produced by neutron activation of ^{152}Sm [4].

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Ross, et al. established the first TRIGA digital twin at UT Austin for short-timescale state reconstruction (microseconds to minutes) using POD with Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) and Dynamic Mode Decomposition (DMD) methods [5]. Medical isotope campaigns, however, unfold over hours to days and are dominated by $^{135}\text{Xe}/^{149}\text{Sm}$ kinetics, temperature feedback, and control rod height variations. The MIP-DT extends the UT Austin digital twin initiative into this planning regime with three main contributions: (1) a direct-mapping surrogate from operating conditions to POD coefficients that eliminates temporal error accumulation; (2) six coupled physics modules that close the neutronics–thermal–depletion loop in real time; and (3) we answer the planning question absent from prior nuclear digital twins: *how should we operate the reactor to deliver a specific isotope, at a specific activity, by a specific time?*

Figure 1. Top-down view of the UT Austin's NETL TRIGA reactor. The medical isotopes are produced in locations CT and 3EL locations (shown with the purple and yellow stars in the last picture).

2. HIGH-FIDELITY MODELING FRAMEWORK

2.1. VERA/MPACT and the 2D TRIGA Model

The Michigan Parallel Characteristics Transport code (MPACT) is the pin-resolved neutron transport solver in the Virtual Environment for Reactor Applications (VERA) core simulator. It employs a 2D/1D method: planar Method of Characteristics (MOC) radially, coupled to an axial P_3 nodal expansion, with 3D coarse-mesh finite difference (CMFD) acceleration [6]. Cross sections are processed from the SCALE/AMPX 51-group library [7].

The training data for this work are generated from 2D radial MPACT calculations of the TRIGA core. This formulation resolves every fuel pin, control rod, irradiation position, and reflector region at pincell-level spatial fidelity, with the geometry implicitly infinite in the axial direction. The 2D approach was adopted as a deliberate proof-of-concept: the dominant physics governing isotope planning—control rod worth variations, spatial flux redistribution, and irradiation-site sensitivity—are primarily radial phenomena in the hexagonal TRIGA geometry. Each 2D solve completes in sub-second timeframes, rather than hours, enabling the generation of the large training ensembles required to sample the operational parameter space. The missing axial leakage is corrected during DT evaluation via a geometric buckling term $B_z^2 = (\pi/H_{\text{ext}})^2$. Extension to full 3D MPACT models is planned as future work.

2.2. Training Data Generation

There were 383 individual 2D MPACT cases that were automated, systematically varying:

- Control rod positions: TR, RR, S1, S2 (each 0–1000 steps),
- Power histories, and therefore, fission product poisons: ^{135}Xe and ^{149}Sm number densities,
- Irradiation target: ^{152}Sm mass (0.5–3 mg) at the Central Thimble (CT) and/or 3EL positions.

Each run produces pin-resolved fast and thermal flux distributions stored in HDF5 format, along with homogenized cross sections and k_{eff} .

(a) Cross-sectional geometry of the quartz ampule containing the ^{152}Sm target.

(b) MOC rays traversing the target region; rays may miss the physical ampule due to its small size.

Figure 2. MPACT ray tracing geometry for the ^{152}Sm irradiation target.

Each ray must go through the geometry/material region shown in Figure 2b. Note that it is possible that a sample might be too small that a ray does not pass through it at all. The ^{152}Sm isotope radius is ≈ 0.003756 cm, which is too small relative to the MOC ray spacing of 0.05 cm. As of the writing of this paper, MPACT did not have a way to model this type of geometry explicitly, thus needing a volume-averaged target. We employ a volume-weighted homogenization (“smear”) that preserves cell-averaged reaction rates while ensuring adequate ray coverage. The target is optically thin at its physical dimensions, so self-shielding corrections are negligible. For training, all ^{152}Sm samples were either 0.5mg, 1mg, 2mg, or 3mg inside an ampule made up of quartz placed in the central thimble or 3EL region in the TRIGA.

3. SVD/POD AND MACHINE LEARNING PIPELINE

3.1. Snapshot Matrix and Decomposition

Let $\mathbf{x}_j = \text{vec}(\phi_j^{\text{fast}}, \phi_j^{\text{thermal}}) \in \mathbb{R}^N$ ($N \approx 7,000$) be the power-normalized, two-group flux distribution for snapshot j . We define the mean-centered snapshot matrix

$$\tilde{\mathbf{X}} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_m] \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times m}, \quad (2)$$

and compute the thin SVD $\tilde{X} = \mathbf{U}\Sigma\mathbf{V}^\top$. Truncating to the first r modes ($r = 6$) yields the POD basis $\mathbf{U}_r \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times r}$, and any flux field is approximated as

$$\Phi \approx \mathbf{U}_r \boldsymbol{\theta}, \quad \boldsymbol{\theta} \in \mathbb{R}^r. \quad (3)$$

Figure 3. First 6 POD modes showing fast flux (top) and thermal flux (bottom).

Figure 3 shows the first six POD modes: Mode 1 captures the fundamental flux shape; Modes 2–5 resolve control rod perturbations; Mode 6 captures flux sensitivity at the CT and 3EL irradiation sites.

3.2. Operating-Conditions State Vector

Our DT follows these high level guidelines:

1. The input space is parameterized in terms of the relevant TRIGA operating degrees of freedom: four control rod positions, power, target sample placement, temperature feedback, and poison states, shown in Eq 4.
2. The training distribution includes operationally realistic maneuvers (startup, irradiation holds, power changes, and shutdown).
3. The justification for this approach is pragmatic and epistemic: the DT must be fast enough for operational decision support, yet anchored to a simulation engine that enforces neutron balance and consistent nuclear-data closure when generating the labeled dataset.

The DT training task is fundamentally a supervised learning problem over reactor state. Let the operating state be represented by

$$\boldsymbol{\zeta}_{ops}(t) \equiv \left[\underbrace{k}_{\text{reactivity}}, \underbrace{\phi_i}_{\text{group flux}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{r}_i(t)}_{\text{rod heights}}, \underbrace{P(t)}_{\text{power}}, \underbrace{\mathbf{T}(t)}_{\text{temperature}}, \underbrace{N_i(t)}_{\text{isotopes}}, \underbrace{\text{location}}_{\text{of the target}} \right] \quad (4)$$

and let the high-fidelity model map this state to outputs used by the DT (e.g., flux fields, eigenvalue/reactivity proxies, and reaction-rate fields),

$$\mathbf{y}(t) \equiv \mathcal{H}(\boldsymbol{\zeta}(t)) = \left[\phi_g(\mathbf{r}), k_{\text{eff}}, R_x(\mathbf{r}), \dots \right]. \quad (5)$$

VERA/MPACT provides a deterministic approximation to $\mathcal{H}(\cdot)$ that is sufficiently stable and efficient to generate *ensembles* of labeled snapshots $\{\boldsymbol{\zeta}_j, \mathbf{y}_j\}_{j=1}^m$ at scale, which is the central requirement for

POD/SVD-based ROMs and downstream ML regressors. Expanding the $\xi_{ops}(t)$ vector further, we get Equation 6, where all variables are changing with time.

$$\xi_{ops}(t) \equiv \left[k, \phi_{th}, \phi_{fast}, CR_1, CR_2, CR_3, CR_4, P, T, N_{135Xe}, N_{149Sm}, N_{153Sm}^{CT}, N_{153Sm}^{3EL} \right] \quad (6)$$

For our DT development, VERA MPACT simulations are used for training and evaluation with these key metrics: (1) understanding multigroup scalar flux $\{\phi_g(\mathbf{r})\}$, pin power, assembly power, and regionwise reaction rates. (2) understanding eigenvalue k_{eff} (or an equivalent reactivity proxy), control rod worth curves (by perturbation sequences); (3) feedback variables like fuel/moderator temperatures (or effective temperature fields), coolant densities, and other state quantities needed for cross-section closure; (4) obtaining cross-section data; and (5) For each scenario, the coupled DT with the diffusion solver is able to compute updated flux and k_{eff} at each time step, and there is a Bateman equation ODE solver that tracks a core-averaged Xe/Sm poison buildup. Furthermore, for medical isotope production planning, the DT must predict time-integrated irradiation outcomes (e.g: activity, specific activity) while remaining consistent with operational constraints (rod worth, temperature limits, scheduled run windows). The goal is not “perfect reconstruction of every microscopic field” but rather a reliable, fast, end-to-end forecasting tool that converts operating decisions into irradiation outcomes (e.g., ^{153}Sm yield) with quantified error at timescales relevant to experiment scheduling and patient supply chains.

3.3. Machine Learning Model: LightGBM

This work employs LightGBM (Light Gradient Boosted Machine), a high-performance GBDT implementation originally developed by Microsoft Research [8]. LightGBM employs a leaf-wise tree growth strategy (as opposed to the level-wise strategy used by many other implementations), which tends to produce deeper, more accurate trees for a given computational budget, at the cost of increased overfitting risk that must be managed through regularization (maximum depth constraints, minimum samples per leaf, L_1/L_2 penalties on leaf values).

For the MIP-DT, a LightGBM model is trained for each POD coefficient $\theta_i, i = 1, \dots, r$. This per-coefficient training strategy allows each model to specialize: the first few coefficients (corresponding to the dominant flux modes) may require different tree depths, learning rates, and regularization strengths than the higher-order coefficients that capture finer-scale features.

Figure 4. LightGBM training performance: parity plots for POD coefficients, (a) normalized and (b) raw.

The parity plots show that the LightGBM predictions are very close to the actual MPACT predictions.

Figure 5. LightGBM training performance (continued): (a) coefficient error distribution and (b) spatial flux error at CT and 3EL locations.

4. RESULTS

We compare high-fidelity MPACT outputs to predictions from our digital twin (DT) across (4) main irradiation cycles and sample sizes (0.5mg, 1mg, 2mg, 3mg):

1. Continuous full-power irradiation for 31 hours (one day), no scheduled off period.
2. Daily cycles of 8 hours on, 16 hours off for five days.
3. Two days of 16-hours-on/8-hours-off cycling.
4. Three days of 12-hours-on/12-hours-off cycling.

(a) Difference in DT and MPACT results.

(b) Relative flux error at irradiation sites.

Figure 6. Distribution of absolute differences in predicted activity in the Central Thimble (CT) and 3EL locations.

Figures 6 quantify the end-of-irradiation between the DT-predicted and MPACT-computed ^{153}Sm activities at the CT and 3EL positions aggregated over all time steps and operating conditions in the validation set. The absolute difference distribution (Figure 6a) shows that the CT predictions are tightly centered like a Gaussian, whereas the 3EL position exhibits a broader spread, extending to $\approx \pm 30$ mCi with a slight positive bias (DT overpredicting relative to MPACT) and a heavier right tail. This wider distribution at 3EL is consistent with the position's location farther from the core center, where flux gradients are steeper and the POD basis must capture more spatial variability with the same number of modes. The relative error distribution (Figure 6b) reinforces this contrast. At the CT location, the overwhelming majority of predictions fall below 5% relative error, with the distribution sharply peaked in the lowest bin. At 3EL, the bulk of the distribution spans 0–25%, with a tail extending to 50–70% and scattered outliers at higher values.

The large relative errors in the tail warrant examination: we believe they occur predominantly at early time steps where the absolute MPACT activity is small (the target is just beginning to activate), so even modest absolute differences of a few millicuries produce large relative errors when divided by a near-zero denominator. At clinically relevant activity levels — i.e., the later time steps when the sample approaches its target dose — the relative errors contract substantially. This observation motivates reporting both absolute and relative metrics, and suggests that for planning purposes the absolute difference (roughly $\pm 20\text{mCi}$ at CT, $\pm 40\text{mCi}$ at 3EL for the central 90% of predictions) may be the more operationally meaningful figure of merit than the relative error. These results are for the 2D MPACT case and smeared medical isotope material definitions.

Figure 7. Predicted ^{153}Sm Activity of Digital Twin and MPACT

As an example of the comparison between MPACT and the DT, Figure 7 shows the activity of ^{153}Sm during a 5 day irradiation campaign where the reactor operates for 8 hours and is shutdown for 16 hours. The difference between MPACT and the DT compares very well over the entire irradiation history.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have presented a digital twin for ^{153}Sm medical isotope production on the UT Austin TRIGA reactor. We showed a direct-mapping surrogate ($\zeta_{\text{ops}} \rightarrow \theta$) that reconstructs the full $\sim 7,000$ -DOF spatial flux field in milliseconds, avoiding temporal error accumulation. The current 2D proof-of-concept validates the methodology and demonstrates operational value. Future work includes: a full 3D MPACT model to resolve axial flux profiles and target positioning; hyperparameter optimization via Optuna or DeepHyper; expansion to other isotopes such as ^{177}Lu and ^{90}Y ; and experimental validation against historical NETL irradiation campaign data. The architecture is designed to be portable to the fleet of 66 TRIGA reactors worldwide and adaptable to other reactor types.

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